

Digital Transformation as one of the Local Strategic Development Drivers: A Case of Dnipropetrovs'k Region

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Abstract. The article highlights particular results of the research carried out in May-June 2019 in the framework of the regional Program of informatization “Electronic Dnipropetrovs'k region” for 2020-2022 development. The integrated digital readiness assessment of 59 amalgamated territorial communities and 11 cities of Dnipropetrovs'k region was obtained by expert method. On the basis of this assessment, as well as the processing of these territorial communities' residents, representatives of business structures and local self-government bodies questionnaire survey results, the results of a comprehensive study of digital technologies implementation and Dnipropetrovs'k region subregions' digital inequality were determined. The results of the study show that there are considerable differences in the content, informativeness and convenience of using amalgamated territorial communities and city councils web-sites as one of the e-democracy and e-governance main tools. The results of the study are taken into account in determining the region informatization main directions for the next three years. It is suggested to use the program-based approach to digital technologies implementation in local self-government bodies. Application of program-targeted approach to digital technologies' implementation in local self-government is proposed. Recommendations for the three phases of a typical program for amalgamated territorial community governing bodies' digital transformation were developed.

1 Introduction

The reform of decentralization of power has been recognized as one of the most successful reforms carried out in the last five years in Ukraine. Dnipropetrovs'k is a leading region along this path – 73 amalgamated territorial communities (ATC) were created in the region in 2015-2019. In 2020, the process of territorial communities' voluntary amalgamation (village, settlements, cities councils), as well as the voluntary association of new village councils with existing amalgamated territorial communities continues. The specific features of the municipalities' formation are caused by other processes of transformation taking place in the state, in particular the integration of Ukraine into the information society.

Modern scientific thought defines the information society and the role of public administration bodies in it as a new stage of human development, in which any person can

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receive, process and disseminate information through Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and the state must ensure a high quality level of informatization of all industries [1].

In the practically all newly created amalgamated territorial community's development strategies of Dnipropetrovs'k region, the mission of the local self-government body (village, settlement, city councils) is to provide the most favourable conditions for territories economic development, support of entrepreneurship and comprehensive development of each individual.

The information society in Ukraine today has reached the stage where digital technologies have already become a part of everyday life and professional activity of almost every person – information search through the Internet, management of all aspects of production using ICT, e-commerce, increasing use of various gadgets in households, e-services etc.

The more ICTs are developed and implemented across all aspects of life, the faster changes the socio-economic environment in which citizens live and businesses operate, the more competitive will be the economy of the amalgamated territorial communities, the region and the country as a whole, and the better living and self-development conditions for everyone citizen will set.

Digitization in this context is understood as a profound activity transformation of an organization, community, territory, industry, which involves the use of digital technologies to optimize business processes, increase productivity, create new models of interaction with stakeholders. Today, digitization is a common trend in the development of Ukrainian society, progress and transition to a new civilization stage [2–6].

In an age of such rapid changes in the socio-economic sphere, the widespread ICTs implementation into the business and ordinary citizens life, amalgamated territorial communities' public authorities must also change according to the requirements of the times. If they do not adopt the “game new rules” and do not actively participate in the digitization processes of authorities and the Ukrainian society as a whole, there is a great risk that the amalgamated territorial communities, cities and regions' self-government bodies, from the driving force of reforms may turn into a brake on social progress.

The main purpose of the local self-government bodies digitization is to fully meet the needs of both business entities and ordinary citizens –public services clients, which expect from public authorities to create a more comfortable environment of operational interaction in the triangle “community – business – government”.

The article highlights some results of the research, which was carried out with the authors participation in May-June 2019 by the Dnipropetrovs'k Regional Institute for Public Administration, National Academy of Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, within the framework of the Regional program of informatization “Electronic Dnipropetrovs'k region” for 2020-2022 draft development [7].

2 Data and Methods

The study of the current state and main problems of digitization processes implementation in local self-government bodies and e-democracy processes' development on this basis were carried out on data aggregated from territorial communities, obtained from official sources and during strategic sessions [8]. Data collection and processing was carried out on the basis of a special advanced methodology developed by Dnipropetrovs'k Regional Institute for Public Administration NAPA [9].

The study of the implementation of e-democracy and e-government tools level as a basis for providing public services in electronic form was carried out on the basis of a methodology developed by a coalition of non-governmental organizations: NGO “Podil Regional Agency for Regional Development”, Association of Ukrainian Cities, Association

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of Local Self-Government Bodies “Ukrainian E-Government Cities”, NGO “European Dialogue”, Civic Network “OPORA”[10].

Information was collected in such areas as “Internet Access”, “Development of Information and Telecommunication Structure”, “Electronic Document Management”, “Electronic Governance”, “Electronic Democracy”, “ICT in Education, Medicine, Libraries and Museums”.

The information, accessibility and convenience of using Dnipropetrovs’k region 59 amalgamated territorial communities and 11 city councils’ websites as the main tool of e-democracy and e-governance were separately evaluated. The rating was made on a 4-point scale (from 0 points – information (service) is missing, up to 3 points – information is complete) in the following categories:

- “Access to information”, subcategories: “Information on City Council activities” (43 indicators), “Information on city, settlement, villages’ infrastructure and livelihoods” (7 indicators), “Documents recommended for placement” (32 indicators);
- “Public Feedback” (12 indicators);
- “Administrative Services” (12 indicators);
- “Public Information Access (including discarded data)” (13 indicators);
- “Website usability” (9 indicators).

3 Presentation of the main results

The results of the survey indicate a significant unevenness of the current state of ICT development in cities and urban areas of Dnipropetrovs’k region. Even at such a basic level of communications as Internet access, the integrated indicator has disagreements across the subregions from 0.30 to 2.90.

Analysis of the city councils' websites by their completeness, services fullness and convenience of use showed that no city council in Dnipropetrovsk has a site that can be considered as a reference. The best websites have the Dnipro city (the center of the region) and the city of Kamyans’ke (a large industrial city, which has the third largest population in the region and a leader in the field of administrative services providing). But these websites also have some drawbacks. For example, the site of the Dnieper City Council lacks the ability to: post a comment via the social network, comment on news and information messages, download application forms for administrative services and track the status of processing these applications, request public information via email, evaluate the website

The discrepancies between the best and worst city council sites are quite significant, and they are 4.4 times quantified by the integrated assessment (in points) (Fig.1).

Similar discrepancies were observed in the evaluation of 59 amalgamated territorial communities’ websites (the rest of the amalgamated territorial communities haven’t got their own sites at the time of the study, due to their recent creation). Websites of the most advanced in this sense amalgamated territorial communities scored an integral score of more than 200 points: Zelenodols’k ATC (234 points) and Slobozhans’ka ATC (202 points), outsider sites scored less than 60 points – Mykolaivs’ka ATC of Vasylykivs’ky District and Karpivs’ka ATC (57 points each), Mezhyrits’ka ATC (55 points), Aul’s’ka ATC (52 points), Ukrainian ATC (27 points).

The results of a comparison of community website activity and residents’ satisfaction with standard of living and business conditions indicate that 80 % are directly proportional to dependency – in communities where the activity of filling, updating and using the official website is higher, the average statistical rating of residents’ living standards and business satisfaction are also higher.

Considering the impact of the Ukrainian society transformation processes into «information society» and the requirements for the e-democracy and e-governance development in the country, one of the priority tasks of the regional program of

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informatization “Electronic Dnipropetrovs’k region” should be to reduce the digital inequality of cities and ATCs.

Fig. 1. Integral assessment of Dnipropetrovs’k region city councils web-sites quality and functionality

Coordinated efforts at the region and municipal levels are required to address this challenge. The strategic vision, the system of strategic and operational goals for the development of each ATC, especially those that are outsiders in the processes of digitization, should reflect the features of socio-economic development based on the advancing development of ICT.

Digitization processes’ development determines the development prospects for e-democracy not only in Ukraine as a whole, but also the formation of an environment and tools for e-democracy at the basic level of society – at the level of municipalities, city councils, amalgamated territorial communities’ town and village councils.

Effective use of the e-democracy toolkit provides an opportunity for each member of the amalgamated community to participate in the formation and implementation of state policy, community self-government bodies decision-making (which is especially important), while providing opportunities for bilateral interactive communication between the public authorities and every citizen.

Development of e-democracy tools is dynamic and broad enough in terms of its content and syllabic. The following tools of e-democracy are widely used: individual and collective e-petition, e-complaint, e-proposal (comment), e-statement, e-initiative, e-consultation, e-discussion, e-meeting, e-poll, e-voting, e-referendum, e-plebiscite, e-elections, e-parliament, e-law, e-justice, e-mediation etc. [11].

As result of the research, a typical stages of amalgamated territorial community governing bodies’ digital transformation process are proposed (Fig. 2).

Phase 1. Business processes analysis.

Community self-government body business processes’ analysis in which it is necessary to determine the effectiveness of each of body’s units, business processes of public services providing, applied technologies of internal and external communications. The next step should be to define the goals and results of the program – to increase the efficiency and transparency of the self-government body’s activities.

Fig. 2. Typical stages of amalgamated territorial community governing bodies’ digital transformation process

This stage is very important in terms of minimizing transformational risks, so it is necessary to approach as carefully as possible the goals and objectives decomposition processes, defining activity functional areas to formulate operational goals, and in the next “SMART goals” stage defining policies for their achievement, etc.

The main goal of the stage should be to simplify and improve the efficiency, transparency and controllability of business processes in self-government bodies, the of digital technologies development for communication with public services’ clients.

If there are not enough people in the communities self-governing bodies with appropriate qualifications in the field of strategic and project management, as well as information technologies, it is advisable to involve third-party experts at this stage.

Phase 2. Digital technologies implementation.

At this stage, it is advisable to apply the project approach as a proven and practical activity that has proven effective in reengineering the organization’s business processes.

At this stage a clear action-plan should be defined, specialists of the necessary qualification selected, the necessary material resources determined. Only then the projects started to implement. Its important to note that it will take some time for the new digital technologies to lead to the desired result – it is necessary to carry out the stages of testing, correcting technical errors, training staff / clients to work with services, etc. Therefore, changes in the activities of the self-government body of cities and the city district and the creation of new development prospects for communities should not be expected immediately after receiving the project product.

Therefore, it is not expected to change the activities of the self-governing bodies of cities and amalgamated territorial communities and to create new development prospects for communities immediately after receiving the product of the project.

Phase 3. Implementation results analysis.

After implementation of each digital decision, it is necessary to analyse its effectiveness and to make sure that it brings additional benefits, first of all, socially oriented, or any other benefit for the amalgamated territorial community and its self-government body. Failure to do so should consider targeting and approaches to implementing specific digital technologies, otherwise they can easily turn from community development tools to the burden of constant, costly expenditures on their budget.

3 Conclusions

At the present stage of information society development in Ukraine, digital transformation is becoming not only a driver but also a vital necessity for both business and the whole public administration system. Therefore, the public administration management at all levels (central, regional, local), when territory development strategic planning, it is necessary to focus on the transition to advance implementation of digital technologies, otherwise self-governing bodies will lose their mission of driving forces of community development.

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